

ASYNCHRONOUS SYSTEM ISSUES IN PARALLEL AND DISTRIBUTED ARCHITECTURE

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ABSTRACT

Parallel and distributed computation is currently an area of intense research activity, motivated by a verity of factors. It is type of computer processing platform that breaks large tasks into smaller pieces that are done at the same time in different places and by different mechanisms. They are sometimes also described as “multi-core” processors. The advent of the Multi Core CPU’s with the blending of the open MPI techniques has give the wings to the distributed computing with assurance of the parallelism.

Keyword: *Parallel computation, Asynchronous system, Distributed Computation, RPC, RMI.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Advancement in electronics and computer architecture has opened new domains of the parallel and distributed computing. The advent of the Multi Core CPU’s with the blending of the open MPI techniques has give the wings to the distributed computing with assurance of the parallelism. Evolution of 3G and 4G with distributed functionality with help of the mobile agent’s technology has proof the significance of the autonomy of the software code i.e. distributed nature of the agents. In this chapter we briefly explore the theoretical background asynchronous issues of the parallel and distributed systems along with the theoretical insights of the asynchronous algorithm related to the distributed systems.

2 ARCHITECTURES OF PARALLEL AND DISTRIBUTED SYSTEMS:

Parallel and distributed computation is currently an area of intense research activity, motivated by a variety of factors. There has always been a need for the solution of very large computational problems, but it is only recently that technological advances have raised the possibility of massively parallel computation and have made the solution of such problems possible [2].

According to the Bertsekas et. al. [2], the availability of powerful parallel computers is generating interest in new types of problems that were not addressed in the past. The development of parallel and distributed algorithms is guided by this interplay between old and new computational needs on the one hand, and technological progress on the other.

3. PARALLEL SYSTEM:

In the simplest sense, *parallel system* is the simultaneous use of multiple compute resources to solve a computational problem [5]:

- A problem is broken into discrete parts that can be solved concurrently
- Each part is further broken down to a series of instructions
- Instructions from each part execute simultaneously on different processors
- An overall control/coordination mechanism is employed

It is type of computer processing platform that breaks large tasks into smaller pieces that are done at the same time in different places and by different mechanisms. They are sometimes also described as “multi-core” processors. This type of system is usually very efficient at handling very large files and complex numerical codes [4]. It’s most commonly seen in research settings where central server systems are handling a lot of different jobs at once, but can be useful any time multiple computers are doing similar jobs and connecting to share infrastructures simultaneously [3]. They can be difficult to set up at first and can require a bit of expertise, but most technology experts agree that, over the long term, they’re much more cost effective and efficient than their single-computer counterparts [4].

According to the author’s [2], various parameters that can be used to describe or classify a parallel computer. We refer as:

- a. **Type and Number of Processors:** There are parallel computing systems with thousands of processors. Such systems are called massively parallel, and hold the greatest promise for significantly extending the range of practically solvable computational problems. A

diametrically opposite option is coarse-grained parallelism, in which there are small numbers of processors; say of the order of 10. In this case, each processor is usually fairly powerful, and the processors are loosely coupled, so that each processor may be performing a different type of task at any given time.

- b. Presence or Absence of a Global Control Mechanism:** Parallel computers almost always have some central locus of control. The global control machine is only used to load a program and the data to the processors and each processor is allowed to work on its own thereafter. At the other extreme, the control mechanism is used to instruct each processor. A related popular classification along these lines distinguishes between SIMD and MIMD parallel computers.
- c. Synchronous vs. Asynchronous Operation:** The distinction here refers to the presence or absence of a common global clock used to synchronize the operation of the different processors. Such synchronization is present in SIMD machines; Synchronous operation has some desirable properties: the behavior of the processor is much easier to control and algorithm design is considerably simplified. On the other hand, it may require some undesirable overhead and, in some contexts, synchronization is just impossible. Example, it is quite hard to synchronize a data communication network and, even if this were feasible, it is questionable whether the associated overhead can be justified. Finally it should be noted that a parallel computing system operating asynchronously can simulate a synchronous system.
- d. Processor Interconnections:** A significant aspect of parallel computers is the mechanism by which processors exchange information. Generally speaking, there are two extreme alternatives known as shared-memory and message passing architectures, and a variety of hybrid designs lying in between. A global shared memory can be accessed by all processors. A processor can communicate to another by writing into the global memory, and then having the second processor read that same location in the memory.
- e.** This solves the interprocessor communication problem, but introduced the problem of simultaneous accessing of different locations of the memory by several processors.

A common approach for handling memory access is based on switching system, see figure 2.1, Where a switching system connecting processors P_i to memory elements M_i . Here the information nodes correspond to switches. When a message reaches a switch, it can continue on

either of the two outgoing links, depending on the destination and the routing algorithm being used. But noted that in figure 2.1, there are two alternative paths from each processor to each memory element, used to reduce the probability that two processors simultaneously attempt to utilize the same link. Such redundancy improves reliability, and provides some flexibility which reduces congestion. On the other hand we refer, the complexities of such switching systems have to increase with the number of processors; this is reflected in longer memory access times.

Figure: 2.1 A Switching system connecting Processors [2]

According to the Bertsekas and Tsitsiklis, we refer that there is no shared memory, but in each processor has its own memory or also called local memory. Processor communicates data through interconnection communication medium, either direct communication or bidirectional communication medium, as shown in figure: 2.2. Which processors are connected together, in this approach all processors were directly connected to the each other, but this connection network is very much expansive and not feasible, either there are an excessive number of connections.

Figure: 2.2 represent a set of processors P_i , each one connected with its own memory and clocks.

3.1 REPRESENTATION OF PARALLEL SYSTEM:

Here, we present parallel system model. All systems are interconnected with any physical network medium. And, passes messages continuously T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4, T_5 through different link. Remember one think is that at polynomial time this (see figure: 2.1) communication is synchronous but when the time is different those parallel system also work as asynchronously. That means only one difference between synchronous and asynchronous system is time slices.

Figure: 2.3 Parallel System Model

3.2 ISSUES OF PARALLEL SYSTEM:

Effective implementation of parallel system involves follows issues: [6]

- Structuring tasks so that certain tasks can execute at the same time (in parallel).

- Preserving the sequencing of tasks which must be executed serially.

3.3 CHARACTERISTICS OF PARALLEL SYSTEM:

A parallel processing system has the following characteristics: [6]

- Each processor in a system can perform tasks concurrently.
- Tasks may need to be synchronized.
- Nodes usually share resources, such as data, disks, and other devices.

3.4 GOALS OF PARALLEL SYSTEM:

We can measure the performance goals of parallel processing in terms of two important properties:

SPEEDUP: It is the extent to which more hardware can perform the same task in less time than the original system. With added hardware, speedup holds the task constant and measures time savings.

Figure: 2.4

At time T_n 100% executed task perform by single machine H_i

At time T_n 50% executed task perform by Parallel machine H_1 & H_2

Figure: 2.4 shows how each parallel hardware system performs half of the task compare to single system on a given interval of time.

With good speedup, additional processors reduce system response time. You can measure speedup using this formula:

$$\text{Speedup} = O_T \div P_T$$

Where, O_T = Machine Original time, and

P_T = Machine Parallel Time.

The P_T is the elapsed time spent by a larger, parallel system on the same task. **Example;** Here we assume that the original system took 48 seconds to perform a task, and two parallel systems took 24 seconds, then the value of speedup would equal 2. However, we can not measure direct, linear speedup. Instead, speedup may be more logarithmic, i.e., assume the system can perform a task of size " T_x " in time duration of " T_t ". But, for a task of size $2T_x$, the system may require time duration of $3T_t$. Remember that, for most OLTP (*on-line transaction processing*) applications, no speedup can be expected, only scaleup. The overhead due to synchronization can, in fact, cause speed-down.

SCALEUP: It is expresses that, how much more work can be done in the same time period by a larger system. With added hardware, a formula for scaleup holds the time constant, and measures the increased size of the job which can be done. See figure: 2.5. If transaction volumes grow and you have good scale-up, you can keep response time constant by adding hardware resources such as CPUs. Also we can measure scaleup using this formula:

$$\text{Scaleup} = P_v \div O_v$$

Where, P_v = Machine parallel volume, and

O_v = Machine original volume.

The P_v is the transaction volume processed in a given amount of time on a parallel system. **Example;** if the original system processes 250 transactions in a given amount of time and the parallel system processes 500 transactions in this amount of time, then the value of scaleup would be equal to 2. A value of 2 indicates the ideal of linear scaleup, when, twice as much hardware can process twice the data volume in the same amount of time.

At time T_n 100% executed task perform by single machine H_i

At time T_n 200% executed task perform by Parallel machine H_1 & H_2

Figure: 2.5 show the Scaleup of original and parallel processors

3.5 BENEFITS OF PARALLEL SYSTEM:

- **Enhanced Throughput:** If tasks can run independently of one another, they can be distributed to different CPUs or nodes and you can achieve scaleup: more processes can run through the database in the same amount of time. If processes can run ten times faster, then the system can accomplish ten times more in the original amount of time. The parallel query feature.
- **Improved Response Time:** in parallel system parallel query can attain speedup with parallel processing, in each transaction parallel system can run faster. For online transmission processing applications, no speedup can be expected, only scaleup. With online transmission processing applications, each process is independent. Even with parallel processing, each insert or update on an order table still runs at the same speed.

4. DISTRIBUTED SYSTEMS:

According to our view, the word distributed in terms such as “distributed system”, “distributed programming”, and “distributed algorithm” originally referred to computer networks, where individual computers were physically distributed within same geographical areas. The terms are now a day used in a much wider sense, even referring to autonomous processes that run on the same physical computer and internet with each other by message passing, while there is no single definition of *distributed system*:

- ✓ There are several autonomous computational entities, each of which has its own local memory.
- ✓ The entities communicate data with each other by using message passing. (The words *message-passing* means, “Passing data between ones to another by through communication medium either wired or wireless medium.”)

A distributed system may have a common goal, such as solving a large computational problem. Alternatively, each system may have its own memory and clocks which can be not shared by any other system. In the other hand we can say, the purpose of the distributed system is to coordinate the use of shared resources or provide communication services to the users. Another way of explanation of distributed system, a distributed system is a collection of cooperating computers. In the past two decades, the use of distributed systems has increased dramatically [8]. Such systems have several advantages over uniprocessors, such as improved performance and increased fault tolerance [9]. Nowadays, it is feasible to build computer systems with enormous processing capacities by interconnecting many small computers. For example, such a high-performance system is the *distributed ASCI (Advanced School for Computing and Imaging) supercomputer*, a set of four clusters of workstations at Dutch universities interconnected by Asynchronous Transfer Mode (ATM) links. Many compute-intensive applications, such as those found in the areas of weather forecasting, VLSI design, and other numerical computations, can benefit from the capacity of such super clusters. Therefore, distributed systems have become an attractive alternative for expensive supercomputers [78].

We can also explain some other properties of distributed systems:

- a. The system has to tolerate failures in individual computers.

- b. The structure of the system is not known in advance, the system may consist of different kinds of computers and network links, and the system may change during the execution of distributed program.
- c. Each computer has only a limited, incomplete view of the system. Each computer may know only one part of the input.

4.1 REPRESENTAION OF DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM:

Figure: 2.6 DAG Representation of Distributed System

Where, P_1 , P_2 , P_3 , P_4 , P_5 and P_6 are processors. Which are connected with the suitable communication medium shown in figure: 2.6 we will try to explain distributed system by Direct Acyclic Graph, there are all processors interchanging data between ones to another; but, not share there memory and clock. As per our knowledge all processors are located in surrounding of the local and global network. We can also explain distributed system by block diagram. Where all processors are connected with the own memory not connected with other processor memory, but all systems are connected with each other and communicate data with each other. See figure: 2.7 this is another way of representation to explanation distributed system.

Figure: 2.7 Block Representation of Distributed System

In other word we can also says that, *distributed system* are groups of networked computers, which have the same goal for their work. In **distributed computing**; each processor has its own private memory (distributed memory). Information is exchanged by passing message between the processors.

4.2 DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM MODEL:

The System model shown in figure: 2.8, it consists of processors, started as 1,...,n. Processor p has capacity e_p , with

$$e_p > 0,$$

$$p = 1, \dots, n$$

The each processor execution (processing of data) capacity is defined as the speed relative instruction set, which is known as instruction signals. For example, if any processor can execute 8-signals at a part of given interval, thus, the speed of processor are 8-bits. It is relative to a

reference processor unit capacity. The capacity lost due to context switching and to other operating-system elapsed time.

Figure: 2.8 The multi processor model

In this model, it has been assume that, $e_1 \geq \dots \geq e_p$. The total capacity e of the system is defined as:

$$e = \sum_{p=1}^P e_p.$$

A system is called homogeneous when $e_1 = \dots = e_p$

According to the author De Jongh [7], we refer three versions of the system model, representing a broad range of computer architectures: uniprocessors, multiprocessors, and distributed systems.

- **Uniprocessors Model:** It has a single processor. In this data processing system, use first come first-served method for the execution of jobs. And, also use resource sharing see figure: 2.10
- **Multi Processor Mode:** In the multiprocessor system processors share a single job queue. See figure: 2.8, all processors have fast access to this queue. We assume that, if a multi processor data processing system can be transferred tasks from one processor to another processor without cost. Thus, the processors serves which job at firstly is decided by job scheduling.

- **Distributed Model:** In this model see in figure 2.9, the systems have P_n processors connected by networks. Each CPU's is with a single processor and its own memory and clocks. In other words, we can say that, here not consider the interconnection of those multiprocessors.

The main difference is with the multiprocessor systems are that in a distributed system. That means the communications between systems are higher. At last we can say scheduling in distributed systems is much more complicated than in uni-data processing system (uniprocessor) and in multi-data processing system (multiprocessor).

Figure: 2.9 The distributed system model

4.3 NEED OF DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM:

According to the author [8], we use distributed system in day-to-day in the part of our life. Because distributed system provides a user friendly environment. Let explain follows:

- **Geographically Distributed Environment:** The First need is, in many situations, the computing environment itself is geographically distributed. Example; let we consider a banking network. Each bank is supposed to maintain the accounts of its customers. If we have own account in any bank and banks communicate with one another to monitor inter-bank transactions, or record fund transfers from geographically dispersed ATMs.

- **Speedup:** It is the second need of distributed data processing system. The speed of computation in traditional uniprocessors is fast approaching the physical limit. We can also use another alternative technique for deriving maximum and more power is to use multiple processors. Dividing a total problem into smaller sub problems, and assigning these sub problems to separate physical processors that can operate concurrently is potentially an attractive method of enhancing the speed of computation. This approach promotes better scalability.
- **Resource Sharing:** The third major part of need is resource sharing. That means, shared both hardware and software resources. The user of computer H_1 may want to use a laser printer connected with computer H_2 , or the user of computer H_2 may need some extra disk space available with computer H_3 storing a large file. In a network of workstations, workstation A may want to use the idle computing powers of workstations H_2 and H_3 to enhance the speed of a particular computation. The Distributed databases are good examples of the sharing of software resources, where a large database may be stored in several host machines, and consistently updated or retrieved by a number of agent processes. But, remember that, H_1 , H_2 and H_3 are the representation of host-1, host-2 and host-3 computes. See figure: 2.10

Figure: 2.10 Represent Resource Sharing by Local System

- **Fault-Tolerance:** Another need is fault-tolerance, let we explain it by an example; in a system having triple modular redundancy, three identical functional units are used to perform the same computation, and the correct result is determined by a majority vote. A

distributed system thus provides an excellent opportunity for incorporating fault-tolerance and graceful degradation.

4.4 ISSUES OF DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM:

We can explain several issues of distributed system which is related to the distributed data processing systems design. We refer distributed system in general word, “a distributed system is a system, which are connected with more processors located in any where in environment communicate data with each other, but not share there memory and clock” see figure: 2.11 (A), (B), and (C).

Figure: 2.10 (A)

Figure: 2.10 (B)

Figure: 2.10 (C)

Figure: 2.11 Representation of distributed system through the network topologies (a) Ring topology, (b) Tree topology, (c) 3-D cube.

In figure 2.11: (A), P_i is the processor, M_i and C_i is the memory and clocks of those processors, respectively. And edges are connections between two processors. Again in figure: 2.11 (B), here N_i represent same. In figure: 2.11 (C) each black node represents a processor, or red nodes for memory and orange node for clocks of each processor. Because, we know that all machine have its own memory and clock. And, each edge represents the way of communication medium. This is used by the connecting processor and transfer data between ones to another. All tries representation of topology is represent the distributed system and communicate messages in asynchronously.

And also emphasis some fundamentally issues of distributed system. These are following:

- **Knowledge of a process:** As we know that every process has its own address. Each process thus has a myopic view of the system. Then, how the processor knows the process; by its address. The addresses of its immediate neighbors, and the channels connecting itself with its immediate neighbors. In some special cases, process also have knowledge about the size of the network.

- **Network Topology:** A network of processes may either be completely connected, or sparsely connected. In a completely connected network, a *link* also called *channel* exists between every pair of processes in the system. This condition does not hold for a sparsely connected topology. As a result, message routing is an important activity. A link between a pair of processes may be unidirectional or bidirectional. Examples distributed systems which are use sparse topology i.e. trees, rings, arrays, or hypercube shown in Figure; 2.10 (a), (b) and (c).

- **Degree of Synchronization:** The distributed systems center on the notion of synchrony and asynchrony. According to the laws of astronomy, real time is defined in terms of the rotation of earth in the solar system. This is called Newtonian time, which is the primary standard of time.

- **Failures:** The handling of failures is an important area of study in distributed systems. A failure occurs, when a system as a whole, or one or more of its components do not behave according to their specifications. A process may crash, when it ceases to produce any output.

- **Scalability:** An implementation of a distributed system is considered scalable, when its performance can be improved by incrementally adding resources regardless of the final scale of the system. Some systems deliver the expected performance when the number of nodes is small, but fail to deliver when the number of nodes increases.

Apart from above mentioned issues has further subdivided issues they are following –

- **Leader election:** When a number of processes cooperate from solving a problem, many implementations prefer to elect one of them as the leader, and the remaining processes as followers. If the leader crashes, then one of the followers is elected the leader, after which the system runs as usual.
- **Mutual exclusion:** There are certain hardware resources that cannot be accessed by more than one process at a time; for example printer is one of them.
- **Time synchronization:** Local clocks invariably drift and need periodic resynchronization to support a common notion of time across the entire system.
- **Global state-** The global state of a distributed system consists of the local states of its component processes. Any computation that needs to compute the global state at a time T has to read the local states of every component process at time T. That means, local clocks are never perfectly synchronized, computation of the global state is a nontrivial problem.

4.5 CHARACTERISTICS OF DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM:

Author sukumar ghosh talked his book, “*Distributed system: An algorithmic approach*”, follows are the major characteristics of the distributed system

- ✓ Transparency
- ✓ Scalability
- ✓ Reliability
- ✓ Flexibility

4.6 APPLICATIONS OF DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM:

Reason for using distributed systems and distributed computing may include:

- ✓ The very nature of an application may require the use of a communication network that connects several computers. Ex; Data produced in one physical location and required in another location.
- ✓ There are many cases in which the use of a single computer would be possible in principle, but the use of a distributed system is beneficial for practical reasons. Ex; it may

be more cost effective to obtain the desired level of performance by using a cluster, of several low-end computers, in comparison with a single high-end computer.

- ✓ A distributed system can provide more reliability than a non-distributed system, as there is no single point of failure. Moreover, a distributed system may be easier to expand and manage than a monolithic uniprocessor system.

4.7 EXAMPLES OF DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM:

As per our knowledge, the examples of the distributed systems is–

- **World Wide Web:** World Wide Web (www) is a popular service running on the Internet. It allows documents in one computer to refer to textual or non-textual information stored in other computers.
- **Network File Systems:** A local-area network consists of a number of independent computers connected through high-speed links. When we can log into our computer at our office, that system is a part of a local-area network. In many LAN's, a separate machine in the network serves as the file server. Thus, when a user accesses a file, the operating system directs the request from the local machine to the file server, which in turn checks the authenticity of the request, and decides whether access can be granted. This shows that with a separate file server, access to a file requires the cooperation of more than one process, in this case the operating system of the user process and the server process.
- **Banking Network:** Assume that, if we need **2000Rs/-** on a Sunday morning, so I went to a nearby ATM to withdraw some cash. I'm checking account in Jablpur City, but I have two savings accounts, one in Rewa, and the other in Satna. Each bank has set an upper limit of **1000Rs/-** on the daily cash withdrawal, so we use two different bankcards to withdraw the desired cash. These debits are immediately registered in my bank accounts in two different cities and recomputed my new balances.
- **Peer to Peer Network:** Any system used an unconventional way to distribute MP3 files. Instead of storing the songs on a central computer, the songs live on users' machines.

There are millions of them scattered all over the world. When we want to download a song using that one, we are downloading it from another person's machine, and that person could be next-door neighbor or someone halfway around the world. This led to the development of peer-to-peer (P2P) data sharing.

- **Process Control Systems:** Assume that, Industrial plants extensively use networks of controllers to over see production and maintenance. Consider a chemical plant, in which a controller maintains the pressure of a certain chamber to 200 psi. As the vapor pressure increases, the temperature has a tendency to increase, so there is another controller 300 ft away that controls the flow of a coolant. This coolant ensures that the temperature of the chamber never exceeds 200°F. Furthermore, the safety of the plant requires that the product of the pressure and the temperature does not exceed 35,000.
- **Sensor Networks:** The declining cost of hardware, and the growth of wireless technology have led to new opportunities in the design of application specific, or special purpose distributed systems. One such application is a sensor network.
- **Grid Computing:** It is a form of distributed computing that supports parallel programming on a network of variable size computers. At the low end a computational grid can use a fraction of the computational resources of one or two organizations, whereas at the high end, it can combine millions of computers worldwide to work on extremely large computational projects.

5. COMMUNICATION ASPECTS OF PARALLEL & DISTRIBUTED SYSTEMS:

According to Bertsekas & Tsitsiklis, 1989 [2]; many parallel and distributed systems the time spent for interprocessor communication is a sizable fraction of the total time needed to solve a problem. In this case author's say that the algorithm experiences substantial communication penalty or communication delays. For the analysis of communication issues, it is helpful to view the distributed computing system as a network of processors connected by communication links. Each processor uses its own local memory for storing some problem data and intermediate algorithmic results, and exchanges information with other processors in groups of bits called

“Packets” using the communication links of the network. The length of the packets is widely varying, ranging from a few tens of bits, to several thousands of bits.

A shared memory can also be viewed as a communication network, since each processor can send information to every other processor by storing it in the shared memory. According to author’s [1], we refer the communication delays can be divided into follows:

- ✓ **Communication Processing Time:** This is the time required to prepare information for transmission.
- ✓ **Queueing Time:** When information is assembled into packets for transmission on some communication link; it must wait in a priority queue to the start of its transmission for a number of reasons.
- ✓ **Transmission Time:** This is the time required for transmission of all the bits of the packets.
- ✓ **Propagation Time:** This is the time between the end of transmission of the last bit of the packet at the transmitting processor, and the reception of the last bit of the packet at the receiving processor.

Apart from this according to the author, several important factors that influence communication delays are the following:

- ✓ The algorithm used to control the communication network, mainly error control routing, and flow control.
- ✓ The communication network topology, i.e. the number, nature, and location of the communication links.

6. COMMUNICATIONS AMONG DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM:

We have listed various modes of communication among distributed entities:

- **OSI or TCP/IP** model integrating with Naming conventions like DNS to assure naming transparency
- **Remote Procedure Call (RPC)** No message passing is visible to the programmer, this technique is remote procedure call, as shown in figure 2.12.

Figure: 2.12 RPC model

- **Remote Method Invocations (RMI)** is a way that a programmer, using the Java programming language and development environment, can write object-oriented programming in which objects on different computers can interact in a distributed network. RMI (shown in figure: 2.13) is the Java version of that is generally known as a remote procedure call (RPC), but with the ability to pass one or more objects along with the request. The object can include information that will change the service that is performed in the remote computer. For example: Sun Microsystems

Figure: 2.13 RMI Model

- **Message Passing** are the best communication methods in distributed systems of both type i.e., synchronous and asynchronous distributed systems.
- **Group Communications** - Group communication applies to groups containing between three or more the three system. Which can share there data's either wired or wireless communication.
- **Web Services** – It is a method of communication between two electronic devices over a network. It is a software function provided at a network address over the Web with the service *always on* as in the concept of utility computing.
- **CORBA (Common Object Request Broker Architecture)** – It is a standard developed by the Object Management Group (OMG) to provide interoperability among distributed objects. CORBA is the world's leading middleware solution enabling the exchange of information, independent of hardware platforms, programming languages, and operating systems. CORBA is often described as a "software bus" because it is a software-based communications interface through which objects are located and accessed.

7. Conclusion: In this research work, we explain asynchronous system issues in Parallel and Distributed Architecture through block diagram and/or DAG representation, in and, has presents the surveyed the previous work in same domain of the proposed research area. We explore RMI and RPC model through different type architecture. Also, we discuss some theoretical issues related to asynchronous parallel and distributed architecture.

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